

COCKPIT DISPLAYS FOR A KNOWLEDGE-BASED SYSTEM:
THE INTELLIGENT AIR ATTACK SYSTEM

Judith H. Lind

Code 3152, Naval Weapons Center
China Lake, California 93555

ABSTRACT

The Intelligent Air Attack System (IAAS) is a prototype integrated avionics system in the advanced development phase, intended for integration into attack aircraft in the early 1990s. The prototype IAAS will serve as an "assistant" to the crew by helping with three critical tasks: (1) classification of ship targets at long range; (2) detection, identification, and countering or evasion of in-the-air missile threats; and (3) on-the-fly strike management and strike plan modification. IAAS will extract and correlate sensor data from aircraft data bus signals, and fuse it into a "best-picture-of-the-world" data base. After using a knowledge-based program to determine the specific information needed for current tasks, the system will format this information into intuitively-recognizable pictorial displays for rapid, accurate aircrew understanding and response.

INTRODUCTION

The Intelligent Air Attack System (IAAS) is a prototype integrated avionics software system that is presently under development at the Naval Weapons Center (NWC), China Lake, California. It is intended for aircrew use in the F/A-18, A-6, or other Navy or Air Force tactical aircraft in the early 1990s.

The outgrowth of a two-year cooperative research and development project among human factors, radar, and electronic warfare (EW) specialists, the IAAS project now is in the advanced development (6.4) stage. The project is supported by the DoD Joint Service Manpower and Training Technology Development Program. The NWC Human Factors Branch is responsible for overall project and system management.

Aircrew Problems

In the next five years, tactical aircraft sensors may include range-only radar (ROR), inverse synthetic aperture radar (ISAR) or other beyond-visual-range targeting systems; radar warning receivers (RWR); and missile defense

systems (MDS). These sensor systems are capable of providing vast amounts of data about "what's out there, and where it is" -- to an aircrew that already is overloaded with information and tasks.

Navy and Air Force pilots must be able to perform their jobs under conditions of high-speed, low-level flight and severe time compression, while evading deadly enemy threats. The specific problems faced by these tactical pilots have been documented by numerous authors (Ref. 1-3). These problems can be summarized as: vastly increased mental workload, coupled with moderately increased manual workload.

Problems with Automation

Automation of various cockpit functions is frequently proposed as a solution to these workload-related problems. Yet military aviators for the most part are adamantly unwilling to trust their missions and lives to arbitrarily automated systems (Ref. 4). Quite correctly pilots note that missions and situations differ vastly; computers usually are inflexible and unable to take such differences into account.

An automated airborne system must be especially robust. Even so, inevitably there will be failures. An integral failure-detection system is critical, and rapid manual recovery by the aircrew must be facilitated. The failed system somehow must provide assistance as the crew once again takes over control. Loss of skill is almost certain, since automated systems remove the opportunity to practice. For example, commercial pilots have experienced a significant decline in manual flying proficiency, after becoming accustomed to automated systems (Ref. 2).

THE INTELLIGENT AIR ATTACK SYSTEM

IAAS has been developed as a near-term solution for the tactical aircrew's avionics-driven overload of mission information and tasks. System design is based on the needs and desires of the pilots who will use it. As

the Navy's first advanced development AI-in-the-cockpit system, IAAS will demonstrate the degree to which intelligent avionics systems can help reduce workload levels for the tactical aircrew.

IAAS Concepts

IAAS uses conventional and knowledge-based programs to personalize the aircraft's computer-driven systems for a particular strike mission, based on the mission plan and on selections by the pilot (Ref. 5). The overall goal is facilitation of the management of mission tasks: helping the pilot know what to do and when to do it, and assisting him with task execution. Three basic IAAS concepts are

1. Adaptive automation. Different levels of automation are needed for various mission tasks. IAAS does not adapt its own automation levels; instead the pilot personally customizes these levels, before the mission, on a task-by-task basis. Workload will be reduced during the mission, but aircrew decision-making prerogatives will not be usurped. Automation modes include

- a. Inform/Monitor: IAAS provides information that is appropriate for the current tactical situation, and alerts the pilot to an important event or to deviation from plans.
- b. Recommend/Implement: IAAS alerts the pilot to information that is appropriate for the current tactical situation, presents a menu of optional actions to the pilot, and recommends one. The pilot may concur via a switch depression, and IAAS will carry out that option. Or the pilot may select another option and execute the task himself.
- c. Automate: IAAS initiates and carries out a given task autonomously, when predefined conditions are met.

2. Intelligent information management. The computer system will correlate and integrate prebriefed mission data and mission plans with real-time data from multiple onboard sensors and from pilot actions. This will result in the pilot getting the most accurate information possible, without being overloaded with uncorrelated or unneeded data.

3. Status-at-a-glance displays. IAAS display formats are being designed for rapid mental processing. Intuitive understanding of the current tactical situation is the goal, along with rapid and correct pilot decisions and responses.

IAAS Functions

The prototype IAAS will serve as an "assistant" to the aircrew by carrying out several specific functions, upon command.

1. Permission briefing. The IAAS Permission Briefing Subsystem (PMBS) will collect and record information needed for a specific mission (Figure 1). This information will be loaded into the IAAS onboard computer system prior to aircraft launch. Information will include strike plan parameters (targets, weapons, route, etc.) and levels-of-automation instructions from the crew.

Figure 1. IAAS Permission Briefing Subsystem: Schematic Information Flow.

2. Sensor data correlation and multisource information integration. The IAAS Information Integration Subsystem (IIS) will continuously extract sensor data from preprocessors during the mission, via the aircraft data bus (Figure 2). Sensors include the MDS, and the ISAR, ROR, and RWR systems. The IIS then will compare and

Figure 2: IAAS Information Integration Subsystem: Schematic Information Flow.

correlate this real-time data with information provided via the PMBS, and integrate the resulting prebriefed and multisensor data into a current situation, "best-picture-of-the-world" data base. This subsystem uses a knowledge-based program to determine what specific information the crew needs or wants at the moment, then formats that information into intuitively-recognized "situation summary" displays for rapid, accurate aircrew recognition and response.

3. Mission agenda management and task automation. The IAAS Task Support Subsystem (TSS) will monitor the progress of the mission agenda, based on prebriefed information and current situation information (Figure 3). The TSS provides a display of the planned mission agenda (what must be done and when to do it). It also will help the pilot carry out a set of tasks by providing task support displays and the desired levels of automation specified by the aircrew for the mission at hand.

Figure 3. IAAS Task Support Subsystem (TSS): Schematic Information Flow.

IAAS Requirements

A system such as IAAS requires five hardware components, for full operation.

1. Computer system. An airborne computer that can operate knowledge-based system software is required for the IAAS prototype. Continuing development of microprocessors with artificial intelligence capabilities make it likely that such systems should be readily available for use with IAAS by 1990.

2. Prebriefing capability. The most convenient technique for entry of prebriefing data will be via an aircraft "mission loader"

that can accept input from a diskette or cartridge that is prepared aboard the aircraft carrier prior to cockpit entry. Such a system is planned for the F/A-18, in the near future.

3. Onboard sensors. Current information about "what's out there" (ships, missiles, other aircraft) comes from electro-optical (E/O), EW, and radar sensors. A system such as IAAS must be programmed to take advantage of data from the exact sensor suite that is available.

4. Programmable multifunction displays and controls. Head-up and head-down displays are necessary for presentation of the IAAS information display formats. Changes to data and to preselected levels of automation may be entered by the pilot via multifunction pushbutton controls, during the mission. In addition, the pilot may use hands-on-throttle-and stick (HOTAS) controls for selecting options and for approving IAAS-proposed actions.

5. Onboard communication links. IAAS requires up-to-date information from various onboard sources, and also must send out queries and data. Thus an avionics communication bus (MIL-STD-1553) is needed, linking the IAAS computer with mission computers, displays and controls used for IAAS functions, electronic flight controls, processors for onboard sensor data, etc.

DEMONSTRATION PROTOTYPE

IAAS software is being designed for use on an airborne computer to provide assistance to the tactical aircraft pilot during high-stress, high-workload portions of a mission. Although the IAAS concepts are applicable to most Army, Navy, and Air Force aircraft missions (and even to military ground systems), the prototype system is tailored for an F/A-18-like aircraft, operating in a war-at-sea scenario.

Prototype Functions

Specifically, the prototype IAAS system will demonstrate how intelligent computer aiding can help the pilot with three difficult and critical combat identification and mission management functions. Pilot-selected levels of automation, premission briefing data, data bases, knowledge bases, conventional computer programs, and knowledge-based programs are used in the process.

First, the prototype IAAS Antiship Attack Targeting Subsystem (ASATS) can assist with obtaining positive combat identification of ship targets at long range (Figure 4). Sensor data from ISAR, RDR, and RWR systems are used for this process, along with prebriefed information about expected targets and a knowledge-based computer program.

Figure 4. IAAS Antiship Attack Targeting Subsystem (ASATS): Schematic Information Flow.

Second, the IAAS EW Automated Response Subsystem (EWARS) provides assistance for the life-and-death process of detecting, identifying, and either countering or evading in-the-air missile threats (Figure 5). IAAS uses RWR and MDS sensor data, plus a knowledge-based program containing data and rules related to threat identification and countermeasures.

Figure 5. IAAS EW Automated Response Subsystem (EWARS): Schematic Information Flow.

Third, the IIS and TSS display formats and "agenda management" functions will help the pilot modify his strike plan if necessary, while maintaining situational awareness (i.e., where he is in the mission and also where he is in executing a particular mission task). The agenda will be set up during the premission

briefing process. Elapsed time, external events, and pilot actions will be monitored by IAAS to determine that the mission is on schedule. If not, IAAS will alert the pilot and, if he concurs, make necessary modifications and take over unfinished tasks.

Rapid Prototyping Process

IAAS is a quick-response project to meet pilot needs of the next few years. Completion of the IAAS project by 1989 is made possible by severely limiting the scope of what this prototype knowledge-based system will do to aid the pilot. No attempt is being made to create a full-fledged "computerized copilot".

Rapid prototyping is made possible through imposition of the following constraints.

1. System requirements are limited to off-the-shelf equipment and technologies anticipated by 1990.
2. The prototype system is designed for one aircraft (similar to the anticipated 1990 F/A-18) and for one tactical mission (ship attack during a war-at-sea mission).
3. Software is kept simple and mission specific, is limited to IAAS goals, and builds on existing F/A-18 capabilities.
4. Technology will be demonstrated in the laboratory before 1990, using realistic simulation; limited flight tests will follow.

Standard F/A-18 airframe, engines, cockpit, displays, controls, and sensors (tactical and navigation radar, EW) are assumed present for the prototype's simulation programs. In addition, a few non-F/A-18 systems will be simulated, for demonstrations of IAAS's full capability for other aircraft. These systems include the IAAS computer and an ISAR system for ship classification.

IAAS DISPLAY FORMATS

General and specific guidelines for optimum design of human-computer interfaces have been collected and used for development of IAAS display formats and symbol sets (Ref. 6-7). In general, these guidelines represent human factors principles that are intended to help the user understand visual information rapidly and correctly, even when under stressful conditions.

Influence of Existing F/A-18 Displays

The ultimate user of the prototype IAAS's follow-on systems most likely will be an F/A-18 pilot. Thus, new IAAS displays must be cognitively compatible with any existing F/A-18 displays that may be used in the same timeframe (a well-established human factors ground rule).

This requirement for F/A-18 compatibility has been a consistent rule of thumb in IAAS display format development, overriding more general human factors guidelines for good display design. Whenever a choice has had to be made between existing display practice in the F/A-18 and a different (possibly-preferred) information display guideline, the decision has been made in favor of F/A-18 consistency.

Compatibility does not mean that the IAAS display formats simply mimic existing F/A-18 display formats. It does mean that phrases, words, abbreviations, and other symbols that already have been assigned meanings still have the same meanings on IAAS display formats. Information that already has an assigned location on F/A-18 display formats is found in the same general location on IAAS formats, insofar as possible. Multifunction control assignments also are consistent with present practices whether used for IAAS or non-IAAS functions.

F/A-18 Multifunction Display and Control Equipment

Figure 6 illustrates the F/A-18 crewstation, with its multifunction displays and controls.

Figure 6. Standard 1988 F/A-18 Single Pilot Crewstation.

F/A-18 Head-up Display (HUD) and the left and right 5-inch Digital Display Indicators (DDIs) are used for IAAS displays and IAAS-related functions. Although not actually required for IAAS functions, the Horizontal Indicator (HI) situation display and Up-Front Control (UFC) multifunction control panel are used in the same time frame, for performance of the F/A-18 war-at-sea mission.

F/A-18 Display Formats and Symbol Set

The IAAS prototype subsystems do not replace any of the present F/A-18 functions and avionics systems. Rather, IAAS is intended to supplement and augment existing capabilities. As a result, many existing F/A-18 display formats (containing a standard set of symbols) must be simulated for use side by side with the new IAAS display formats in demonstrations and evaluations of IAAS capabilities.

Example standard F/A-18 display format diagrams are illustrated in Figures 7 and 8.

Figure 7. F/A-18 DDI Stores Management Display Format Diagram, when Carrying Two Sidewinder Air-to-Air Missiles and four Harpoon Air-to-Surface Missiles. Twenty pushbuttons are available for selecting options; when in use, the buttons are labeled on the display periphery.

Figure 8. F/A-18 DDI Air-to-Surface "Sea Mode" Radar Display Format Diagram. The aircraft's mission computer has recognized three ships in the radar imagery, and notes their locations in the upper left quadrant. Cursors may be used to select one of these for designation as a target of interest.

IAAS Display Formats and Symbol Set

New F/A-18 capabilities that result from incorporation of the IAAS computer programs require several new kinds of display formats, in addition to the aircraft's existing large catalog of formats. The new formats are being designed for use either with the present monochrome displays or with anticipated full-color display sets that are scheduled for integration into the F/A-18 in the near future.

The symbols used in IAAS display format design generally are identical in shape, size, and meaning to the existing F/A-18 symbol set. This is not a major limitation, however, since the available set is quite large, and other simple symbols can be developed from line segments (chained vectors) if needed.

IAAS format designs are still under development. Actual formats will not be finalized until after operator performance evaluations occur in 1989; preliminary or "notional" display formats are being used during the development process. New display formats designed specifically for the IAAS subsystems will fall into several categories:

1. Permission briefing display formats. The formats in this category are used for data entry into the PMBS. These display formats are presented on the monitor of a standard, IBM-compatible personal computer aboard the aircraft carrier prior to the mission. Data

values are entered using a conventional computer keyboard. Default values, based on prior selections made by the pilot, are provided to minimize data entry.

Strike plan data are used to provide IAAS with an internal representation (model) of the mission profile. This representation, along with knowledge bases of ships, sensors, and weapons, is used to assist the pilot in carrying out appropriate tasks at appropriate times, and to keep the pilot alert to threats throughout the mission.

2. Head-up warnings and alerts. The HUD is a forward-looking display surface; thus, HUD formats always are vertical displays, providing symbols representing areas and objects that are correlated in altitude and azimuth with the view out the windscreen. In addition, a small amount of other critical data also is provided (altitude, airspeed, distance to a waypoint or weapon delivery point, etc.).

Since a HUD is effective only if it is not cluttered, only critical IAAS-related information can be added to this F/A-18 display. Basic existing HUD formats will be used, with the addition of alerting cues as necessary. That is, only EWARS-related missile defense information and TSS alerts to other critical events will be displayed on HUD formats.

3. Situation summary display formats. Correlated sensor and prebriefed information from the IIS will be used to create these display formats (Figures 9 and 10). They will

Figure 9. Preliminary Format for the IAAS Mission Plan Situation Summary Display. The aircraft route is indicated, with waypoints marked. Waypoint 5 has been selected with a cursor to obtain (or change) information about its parameters. Three ships have been located and classified.

Figure 10. Preliminary Format for the IAAS Threat Advisory Situation Summary Display. The types of surface-to-air missiles associated with the three ships are noted, along with missile ranges.

serve the function of helping the pilot orient himself with respect to the outside world. Either a DDI or the HI may be used to provide these plan view (down-looking) summary

displays, in consonance with the location of other horizontal, map-like display formats in the F/A-18 crewstation.

4. Agenda display formats. These formats are based on information from the TSS, which maintains an agenda of mission tasks and expected mission events, based on the premission briefing and its own knowledge base (Figure 11). The formats will serve the function of helping the pilot "keep ahead of the mission", recognizing what must be done and when. The agenda display format resembles an "event flow" diagram, with labeled tasks and events moving from left to right as the mission progresses. Pilot actions and a sequential listing of anticipated events determine agenda progress, rather than a moment-by-moment flow of time.

Figure 11. Preliminary Format for the IAAS Agenda Display. Tasks currently "active" are listed on the right, in priority order; "pending" tasks are on the left. Waypoint 3 tasks and information have been selected for further scrutiny (WYPT 3 boxed); this task is being executed in the INFORM mode, and is running 45 seconds behind schedule. AUTOMATE mode tasks are labeled with a "<" symbol, RECOMMEND mode tasks with "[".

5. Task support display formats. The prototype IAAS (plus associated hardware systems) provides the pilot with several new capabilities. These include: (a) the ability to modify or replan his mission "on-the-fly", (b) long-range ship identification, (c) advanced capability to counter or evade enemy missiles, and (d) use of a cursor or DDI pushbuttons to carry out IAAS functions. Preliminary IAAS display formats have been developed that provide the pilot with necessary information and control configurations needed for carrying out the tasks associated with these capabilities. Examples are shown in Figures 12 and 13.

Figure 12. Preliminary Format for the IAAS Threat Evasion/Countering Task Support Display. IAAS has detected, located, and identified two incoming missiles. Best countermeasures (dispense chaff and jammers) are shown. Since IAAS is in AUTOMATE mode for this task, countermeasures automatically will be dispensed at the proper time (shown by the count-down clocks).

Figure 13. Preliminary Format for the IAAS Ship Classification Task Support Display. The upper ship profile represents the radar image, as processed by IAAS computer programs. The lower image is from IAAS's library of ship profiles (name of ship type boxed), for comparison.

ACRONYMS

AI	Artificial intelligence
ASATS	Antiship Attack Targeting Subsystem
DDI	Digital Display Indicator multi-purpose CRT display
ECM	Electronic countermeasures
E/O	Electro-optical sensor
EW	Electronic warfare
EWARS	Electronic Warfare Automated Response System
HARM	High-speed Anti-radiation Missile
HI	Horizontal Indicator multi-purpose CRT display
HOTAS	Hands-on-throttle-and-stick control philosophy
HUD	Head-up display
IAAS	Intelligent Air Attack System
IIS	Information Integration Subsystem
ISAR	Inverse Synthetic Aperture Radar
MDS	Missile defense system
NWC	Naval Weapons Center, China Lake, California
PMBS	Premission Briefing Subsystem
ROR	Range-only radar
RWR	Radar warning receiver
SAG	Surface action group
TSS	Task Support Subsystem
UFC	Up-Front Control multifunction control panel

REFERENCES

1. R.A. Chorley (1982). "Aircrew and Avionics - Friends or Foes?", in Human Factors Considerations in High Performance Aircraft (NATO AGARD-CP-371), NATO, Loughton, Essex, UK.
2. Committee on Automation in Combat Aircraft (1982). Automation in Combat Aircraft, National Academy Press, Washington, D.C.
3. J.D. Grossman (1983). "Contemporary Problems in Airborne Displays", in Advances in Display Technology III, E. Schlam, ed., 386, pp. 29-31. Bellingham, WA. Available from the SPIE.
4. M.P. Kibbe and R.P. DeVere (1987). Aircrew Opinions on Information Displays and Automation for Electronic Warfare Systems (NWC TP 6782), Naval Weapons Center, China Lake, CA.
5. M.J. Barnes and J.D. Grossman (1985). The Intelligent Assistant Concept for Electronic Warfare Systems (NWC TM 5585), Naval Weapons Center, China Lake, CA.
6. J.H. Lind (1987). Architecture, Automation, and Displays: Human Factors Guidelines for the Intelligent Air Attack System (NWC TM 6156), Naval Weapons Center, China Lake, CA.
7. J.H. Lind (1988). Intelligent Air Attack System: Display Format Diagrams (NWC TM 6207), Naval Weapons Center, China Lake, CA.